

On Bianchi Type Cosmological Models in Lyra's Geometry

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Abstract : Bianchi type cosmological models have been studied on the basis of Lyra's geometry. Exact solution has been obtained by considering a time dependent displacement field for constant deceleration parameter and varying cosmological term of the universe. The physical behavior of the different models has been examined for different cases.

Keywords : Bianchi type-I cosmological model, variable gravitational coupling, cosmological constant term, Lyra's model

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